

Potentiometric Studies on Mixed Ligand Complexes of Gallium(III), Taking NTA as Primary Ligand and Some Aliphatic Carboxylic Acids as Secondary Ligands

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Manuscript received 20 January 1979, revised 8 June 1979, accepted 19 May 1980

Potentiometric studies on some mixed ligand complexes of Ga(III) are reported. Nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) was used as primary ligand whereas, malic acid, maleic acid, malonic acid, succinic acid, oxalic acid and itaconic acid were employed as secondary ligands. $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ was evaluated, using modified form of Irving and Rossotti's method. The stability constant values were found to be in the order, malonic acid \approx maleic acid $>$ malic acid $>$ oxalic acid $>$ succinic acid $>$ itaconic acid. Thermodynamic parameters, e.g. ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° have also been evaluated. Results obtained are correlated on the basis of steric and structural characteristics of the chelates.

IN the last decade several reports have come on the study of mixed ligand complexes of heavier metals¹⁻⁵, but no attempt appears to have been made on the study of mixed ligand complexes of Ga(III) except for a spectrophotometric report⁶. The present communication describes the results obtained in the potentiometric studies of some mixed ligand complexes of Ga(III). Nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) was used as primary ligand (A), whereas malic acid (MA), maleic acid (MAE), succinic acid (SUC), malonic acid (MLA), oxalic acid (OXA) and itaconic acid (ITCA) were employed as secondary ligands (L). The study of binary complexes of these primary as well as secondary ligands with Ga(III) has been reported by earlier workers⁷⁻⁹. The modified method of Irving and Rossotti¹⁰ is applied to determine that $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$. All studies were performed at a constant ionic strength of 0.2M (NaClO₄) and at three different temperature, viz. 15°, 30° and 45°. The thermodynamic parameters ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° were also evaluated.

Experimental

Material: A stock solution of Ga(NO₃)₃·xH₂O(BDH) was prepared in a known quantity of perchloric acid to prevent the hydrolysis of metal ion. The metal content was estimated by the precipitation of Ga(III) as 8-hydroxyquinolate¹¹. Stock solution of 0.01M NTA, 0.2M perchloric acid, 2.0M sodium perchlorate and 0.02M solutions of secondary ligands were prepared in double distilled water and estimated potentiometrically. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide was prepared by standard method¹².

Expanded scale pH meter (accuracy ± 0.02 pH unit) of ECIL fitted with a glass-calomel assembly was used to measure [H⁺] of solution. Saturated

calomel electrode was connected externally by means of an agar-agar salt bridge saturated with KNO₃ to prevent the formation of chloro-complex. Temperature were maintained with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$ by the help of U-10 thermostat. All the experiments were done in an inert atmosphere created by bubbling nitrogen through the solution throughout the course of titration.

Procedure: Four mixtures were prepared as follows:

Mixture A: HClO₄ ($2.37 \times 10^{-2} M$); **Mixture B:** HClO₄ ($2.37 \times 10^{-2} M$) + secondary ligand ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$); **Mixture C:** HClO₄ ($2.37 \times 10^{-2} M$) + metal solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + primary ligand (1.0×10^{-3}); **Mixture D:** HClO₄ ($2.37 \times 10^{-2} M$) + secondary ligand ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + primary ligand ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) + metal solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$). These mixtures were prepared in such a manner that the concentration of common ingredients were identical in each case. An appropriate amount of neutral NaClO₄ was added to maintain the desired ionic strength. The total volume of all systems were kept identical by adding double distilled water. The ratio of M:A:L was kept 1:1:1. A graph between pH-meter reading and volume of alkali added was plotted. The four titration curves so obtained were referred to as: (A) Acid curve, (B) Secondary ligand curve, (C) Primary complexation curve and (D) Mixed ligand complexation curve.

Results and Discussion

Practical Proton-Ligand Stability Constants of Secondary Ligands:

The values of \bar{n}_L at various pH-meter readings were calculated from acid and ligand titration

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curves for secondary ligands. The equation (1) as used by Irving and Rossotti was employed :

$$\bar{n}_A = [YT^{\circ}_{cl} + \frac{(V' - V'')(N + E^{\circ})}{(V^{\circ} + V')}] / T^{\circ}_{cl} \quad \dots (1)$$

where V' and V'' denotes the volume of alkali added to reach the same value of pH in the titration of acid and ligand respectively; T[°]_{cl} is the total ligand concentration; Y is the total number of replaceable protons attached to ligand; N is the normality of alkali used and E[°] the initial strength of acid in the system.

A graph is plotted between \bar{n}_A against pH and practical proton-ligand stability constants were evaluated by (a) the method of interpolation at half \bar{n}_A values and (b) the method of interpolation at various \bar{n}_A values. The values obtained at various temperature and at $\mu = 0.2M$ (NaClO₄) for all these secondary ligands are summarized in Table 1.

Metal-Ligand Stability Constants : In the present case the formation constants have been obtained by plotting \bar{n} against pL. The values of \bar{n} , the average number of ligand molecule attached per metal ion is calculated from equation (2) :

$$\bar{n} = \frac{(V''' - V'')(N + E^{\circ})}{(V^{\circ} + V')\bar{n}_A T^{\circ}_{CM}} \quad \dots (2)$$

where T[°]_{CM} denotes the total concentration of metal ion present in solution, V''' and V'' are the difference in volume of alkali added between curve D and C; B and A respectively to attain the same pH-meter reading. \bar{n}_A is the average number of protons attached to secondary ligand at same pH. The free ligand exponent, pL has been calculated from equation (3) :

$$pL = \log \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{n=j} \beta_n^H (1/\text{antilog } [H^+])^n (V^{\circ} + V''')}{T^{\circ}_{cl} - \bar{n}T^{\circ}_{CM}} \quad \dots (3)$$

where β_n^H is the overall practical proton ligand stability constant and V''' is the volume of alkali required for curve D at the same pH.

From the titration curves (Fig. 1 as an example) it is revealed that the primary complex formation (Curve C) takes place at very low pH and the calculations show that it is stable upto pH 7.5. Primary complex curve C and mixed complex curve D overlap each other at lower pH values indicating that in this range, where primary ligand combines with Ga(III), attachment of secondary ligand does not take place. The mixed complex curve D, separates from primary complex curve C at pH 2.8 due to self dissociation of secondary ligand. After pH 3.0 mixed complex curve shows the indication

Fig. 1. Titration Curve for Ga(III)-NTA-MA mixed ligand Complex at 30°C and $\mu = 0.2M$.

- Curve A : $2.37 \times 10^{-3}M$ perchloric acid ;
- Curve B : $2.37 \times 10^{-3}M$ perchloric acid, $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$. MA ;
- Curve C : $2.37 \times 10^{-3}M$ perchloric acid, $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$. Ga(III) and $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$. NTA ;
- Curve D : $2.37 \times 10^{-3}M$ perchloric acid, $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$. MA, $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$ NTA and $1.0 \times 10^{-3}M$. Ga(III).

Fig. 2. Formation Curve for [Ga(III)-NTA-MA] at different temperatures.

of attachment of secondary ligand with gallium. Since the dissociation of [Ga(NTA)] does not take place in the range of dissociation of secondary ligand, it can be considered that secondary ligand combines with [Ga(III)-NTA]. In presence of secondary ligand the formation of [Ga-NTA-(OH)_n] is also suppressed.

The values of \bar{n} were calculated taking into consideration the difference from curve C and D, (V''') from which the difference of curve A and B (V'') is subtracted at various pH values. A typical plot of \bar{n} against pL for [Ga-NTA-MA] has been shown in Fig. 2. The values of $\log K_{MAL}^M$ have been evaluated using the method (A) interpolation of various \bar{n} values and (B) interpolation of half \bar{n} value. They are summarized in Table 1. The error limits are ± 0.05 log unit. It is however necessary to clear at this point that the above constants calculated here are really not overall mixed ligand stability constants but a step constant for the reaction :

where A is the primary ligand and L is the secondary ligand.

TABLE 1—PRACTICAL PROTON LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Ga(III)-MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES $\mu = 0.2M(\text{NaClO}_4)$

Ligand	pK/log K	Temperature					
		15°		30°		45°	
		A	B	A	B	A	B
MA	$\log K_1^H$	4.64	4.66	4.60	4.59	4.56	4.54
	$\log K_2^H$	3.44	3.45	3.40	3.42	3.34	3.36
	$\log \beta^H$	8.08	8.11	8.00	8.01	7.90	7.90
MAE	$\log K_1^H$	5.72	5.71	5.68	5.70	5.62	5.64
	$\log K_2^H$	3.08	3.10	3.00	3.03	3.02	3.01
	$\log \beta^H$	8.80	8.81	8.68	8.71	8.64	8.65
MLA	$\log K_1^H$	5.15	5.13	5.12	5.10	5.08	5.07
	$\log K_2^H$	3.42	3.41	3.38	3.39	3.32	3.32
	$\log \beta^H$	8.57	8.54	8.50	8.41	8.40	8.39
SUC	$\log K_1^H$	5.22	5.21	5.16	5.18	5.10	5.09
	$\log K_2^H$	4.13	4.15	4.10	4.07	4.08	4.07
	$\log \beta^H$	9.35	9.36	9.26	9.25	9.18	9.16
OXA	$\log K_1^H$	3.93	3.92	3.88	3.85	3.82	3.80
	$\log K_2^H$	1.86	1.85	1.80	1.82	1.74	1.75
	$\log \beta^H$	5.79	5.77	5.68	5.67	5.56	5.55
ITCA	$\log K_1^H$	5.28	5.28	5.22	5.25	5.18	5.21
	$\log K_2^H$	3.92	3.91	3.90	3.87	3.88	3.86
	$\log \beta^H$	9.20	9.19	9.12	9.12	9.06	9.07
[Ga-NTA-MA]	$\log K$	4.85	4.86	4.80	4.78	4.74	4.69
[Ga-NTA-MAE]	$\log K$	5.56	5.58	5.52	5.53	5.49	5.43
[Ga-NTA-MLA]	$\log K$	5.55	5.56	5.53	5.49	5.50	5.45
[Ga-NTA-SUC]	$\log K$	4.37	4.40	4.35	4.33	4.32	4.25
[Ga-NTA-OXA]	$\log K$	4.59	4.61	4.56	4.55	4.52	4.48
[Ga-NTA-ITCA]	$\log K$	3.34	3.38	2.26	3.29	3.18	3.19

Similar titration curves are obtained for other systems and results obtained are also summarized in Table 1.

Thermodynamic Parameters : The values of the change in free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy (ΔS°) have been calculated at three different temperatures and at a constant ionic strength of 0.2 M NaClO₄, with the help of temperature coefficient and Gibb's Helmholtz equation^{1,2}. The value of free energy change (ΔG°), enthalpy change (ΔH°) and entropy change (ΔS°) calculated at three different temperature are summarized in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF Ga(III) MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES $\mu = 0.2M(\text{NaClO}_4)$

System	Temp.	ΔG° K cal/mol	ΔH° K cal/mol	ΔS° e.s.u.
[Ga-NTA-MA]	15°	-6.39	-2.40	+13.8
	30°	-6.61		
	45°	-6.81		
[Ga-NTA-MAE]	15°	-7.34	-1.72	+19.4
	30°	-7.63		
	45°	-7.93		
[Ga-NTA-MLA]	15°	-7.33	-1.71	+19.9
	30°	-7.61		
	45°	-8.09		
[Ga-NTA-SUC]	15°	-6.06	-1.70	+15.1
	30°	-6.29		
	45°	-6.51		
[Ga-NTA-OXA]	15°	-5.79	-2.16	+13.0
	30°	-6.00		
	45°	-6.51		
[Ga-NTA-ITCA]	15°	-4.40	-2.7	+6.0
	30°	-4.55		
	45°	-4.64		

Discussion

The data in Table 2 provides a summary of the results obtained in the present work. The stability constants were found to be in the order $MLA \approx MAE > MA > OXA > SUC > ITCA$. This order may be justified on the basis of (A) ring size of chelate and (B) the structural and donor characteristics of ligand molecule.

MLA forms 6-membered chelate ring, OXA forms 5-membered while SUC, ITCA, MA and MAE form seven membered chelate rings. So the expected trend from Bayer's strain theory will be $MLA > OXA > SUC$, ITCA, MA and MAE. The extra stability of MAE and MA chelate can be attributed to the structural characteristics of the ligands. The presence of conjugate double bond in the MAE chelate ring increases the stability of chelate by exocyclic conjugation while the OH-group present in MA increases the tendency of ligand to give proton at early pH because of its electron-withdrawing tendency. The lower stability of OXA chelate with respect to MA and MAE chelate might also be described due to the high stability of oxalic acid

anion because of resonance, which results in the reduction of complexing behaviour of oxalic acid.

The order of stability constants in 7-membered chelate is MAE>MA>SUC>ITCA. The high stability of MAE and MA chelate is already described while the lower stability of ITCA chelate in comparison to succinic acid chelate might be due to the presence of methyl group in ITCA ligand. This group is electron donating whereby the liberation of proton becomes difficult and the complexing tendencies of the ligand decreases.

The above trend in stability constant were further confirmed by the values of ΔG° obtained during the course of investigation.

References

1. K. N. MUNSHI and T. H. MHASKE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 11.
2. K. N. MUNSHI and T. H. MHASKE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14(A)**, 421.
3. K. N. MUNSHI and A. M. PUJARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 681.
4. D. N. SHELKE and D. V. JAHAGIRDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 545.
5. S. P. SINGH, H. S. VERMA and J. P. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 539.
6. A. P. ZHARKOV, F. YA. KULBA and V. N. VOLKOV, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1977, **22(5)**, 1223 (Russ).
7. R. S. AMBULKAR, Ph. D. Thesis, Nagpur University, Nagpur (1976).
8. R. S. AMBULKAR and K. N. MUNSHI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14**, 424.
9. E. A. BIRYUK and R. V. RAVITSKAYA, *Z. Anal. Khim.*, 1971, **26**, 1752.
10. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
11. L. ERDEY, "Gravimetric Analysis" Inst. Ser. of monographs analyt. Chem. Vol. 7 (Pergamon, New York, 1965).
12. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis" (Longmann Publication, 1971).
13. K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and V. P. VASIL'ER, "Instability Constants of Complex Compounds" (Pergamon, New York, 1960).